

Potential Fungicides. Part—III. Synthesis and Evaluation of 5-Methyl-4-thiazolidinones and 5-Methyl-2,4-thiazolidindiones

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Several new 2-arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (1) and 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindiones (3) have been synthesised and screened for their antifungal activity against *Trichoderma viride* and *Curvularia lunata* at dilutions 1 : 1000 and 1 : 5000 by agar growth food poison technique. The activity was compared to that of a commercially used fungicide Cuman (80% Ziram) and it was found that 3 inhibit the growth of fungus colony more effectively in comparison to the standard. A couple of new 2-arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone-1,1-dioxides (2) were also prepared by KMnO_4 oxidation of 1.

VERY diverse range of biological activities are associated with substituted 4-thiazolidinones¹ and 2,4-thiazolidindiones². Some typical properties they exhibit are local anaesthetic³, antibacterial⁴, antifungal⁵⁻⁸, hypnotic⁹, anticonvulsant¹⁰, anthelmintic¹¹, antiradiation¹² and cardiovascular effects¹³. Furthermore, 1,1-dioxides of 4-thiazolidinones exhibit a significant amoebicidal¹⁴ and anticonvulsant activity¹⁰.

In consideration of such a versatile activity of 4-thiazolidinones, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new 2-(disubstituted)arylimino-3-(disubstituted)aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (1), their 1,1-dioxides (2) and 3-(disubstituted)aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindiones (3), and evaluate their antifungal activity.

The heterocyclic system (1) was synthesised by the interaction of symmetrical 1,3-bis-(disubstituted)phenyl thioureas with equimolar amounts of 2-bromopropionic acid in presence 2 moles of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol (Method A). Alternatively, they were also obtained by the condensation of equimolar quantities of symmetrical 1,3-bis-aryl thioureas with ethyl 2-bromopropionate in presence of 2 moles of pyridine (Method B). Wherever 4-thiazolidinones (1) were prepared by following the procedures A as well as B, the yields of products were practically the same (Table 1). The 4-thiazolidinones give characteristic ir bands at 1730 (m, C=O stretch), 1625 (s, C=N stretch), 1590m and 1500s (aromatic) cm^{-1} .

Oxidation of four typical 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones (1) with potassium permanganate in aqueous acetic acid led to the formation of the corresponding 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinone-1,1-dioxides (2). Their ir spectra show bands at 1310m and 1135m cm^{-1} , which are characteristic of sulphones, in addition to the usual bands.

All the 4-thiazolidinones except 1a were hydrolysed with strong HCl by heating under reflux in ethanolic or acetic acid medium for 6~36 h. Hydrolysis of 1 under such conditions partially cleaved the molecule at position 2 to give the corresponding aniline and 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindione (3) in high yields. The ease with which the hydrolysis takes place, monitored in terms of the reaction time, has been rationalised to throw some light on the mechanism of hydrolysis. The 4-thiazolidinones, that were subjected to hydrolysis, may be broadly classified into three categories.

(i) Compounds (1h, 1i and 1d) having either a *o*- or *p*-methoxy substituent or a *p*-methyl in the phenyl ring of 2-arylimino group, require a relatively short time of 6~10 h to get hydrolysed to the related 3.

(ii) Compounds (e.g. 1b and 1g) having either a *o*-CH₃ or *o*-Cl substituent in the phenyl ring at position 2, require 24~36 h to undergo hydrolysis to the 2,4-thiazolidindione (3).

(iii) Compound 1a in which both the *o*-positions of phenyl ring are substituted by CH₃ and Cl groups,

failed to undergo hydrolysis under similar conditions even after refluxing for a longer period (48 h). Moreover, it did not hydrolyse in boiling glycerol also by heating for 8 h at 270°.

These observations have prompted to propose a mechanism for the hydrolysis of 4-thiazolidinones (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The reaction involves reversible protonation of (1) at the imino nitrogen thereby making carbon at position 2 susceptible to nucleophilic attack by water in a reversible process forming the intermediate (5). The latter by a simple proton transfer gives (6) which eliminates a molecule of substituted aniline to give (3) in a non-reversible process. The formation of intermediates (4) and (6) is apparently favoured by electron-releasing substituents when present at the *p*-position (*e.g.* methoxy or methyl) and that explains the behaviour of **1i** and **1d** towards quick hydrolysis. 4-Thiazolidinones placed in category (ii) exert a combination of steric and electronic effect (inductive, hyperconjugative, *etc.*) of substituents to a varying degree when subjected to hydrolysis. On the other hand, the steric and polar effect of substituents in **1a** was so great that it could not be hydrolysed to corresponding **3a** even under drastic conditions.

Experimental

Melting points were observed with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried on a Coleman Analyser. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 grating spectrophotometer, while nmr on a Varian-A60D instrument at the probe temperature (45°) as CCl₄ or CDCl₃ solutions using TMS as an internal reference. The purity of compounds was checked routinely by tlc using silica gel G (E. Merck).

1,3-Bis-aryl thioureas : These were prepared by modifying the method of Fry¹⁵. A mixture of 2-methyl-3-chloroaniline (14.1 g, 0.10 mol), iodine (12.7 g, 0.05 mol), pyridine (15.8 g, 0.20 mol) and

carbon disulphide (150 ml, 2.5 mol) was heated under reflux on a water bath until the colour of iodine disappeared. The product was steam distilled to remove traces of carbon disulphide and pyridine. The residue was filtered under suction and washed with water to remove pyridinium iodide. It was dried and crystallised from ethanol to give 1,3-bis-(2-methyl-3-chloro)phenyl thiourea (85%), m.p. 190° (Found : C, 55.3 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 8.6 ; S, 10.0. C₁₅H₁₄Cl₂N₂S calcd. C, 55.4 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 8.6 ; S, 9.9%) ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3390m, 3200m (N-H stretching), 1590m, 1540s cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring).

2-(2'-Methyl-3'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (1c) : Method A. A mixture of 1,3-bis-(2-methyl-3-chloro)phenyl thiourea (6.5 g, 0.02 mol), 2-bromopropionic acid (3.4 g, 0.022 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (4.0 g, 0.04 mol) and absolute ethanol (35 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8 h with occasional shaking. After completion of the reaction ethanol was distilled off and the gummy product washed with hot water which solidified on keeping overnight in contact with ice-water. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol to form colourless crystals (48%), m.p. 97° (Found : C, 57.3 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 7.1 ; S, 8.8. C₁₈H₁₆Cl₂N₂OS calcd. C, 57.0 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 7.4 ; S, 8.4%) ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1730m, 1625s, 1590m cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 6.63-7.60 (m, 6H), 4.21 (q, *J* 7Hz, 1H), 1.71 (d, *J* 7Hz, 3H), 2.08 (s, 3H), 2.25 (s, 3H).

2-(2'-Methoxy-5'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (1h) : Method B. A mixture of 1,3-bis-(2'-methoxy-5'-chloro)phenyl thiourea (7.0 g, 0.02 mol), ethyl 2-bromopropionate (3.8 g, 0.021 mol), pyridine (1.6 g, 0.02 mol) and absolute ethanol (35 ml) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 8 h with occasional shaking. Then ethanol and pyridine were removed by distillation and the product was washed with hot water. It solidified on keeping in contact with ice. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol to afford colourless crystals (60%) m.p. 191° (Found : C, 52.5 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 6.9 ; S, 7.7. C₁₈H₁₆Cl₂N₂O₂S calcd. C, 52.6 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 6.8 ; S, 7.8%) ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1730m, 1630s, 1580m, 1500s cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 6.80-7.60 (m, 6H), 4.20 (q, *J* 7Hz, 1H), 1.78 (d, *J* 7Hz, 3H), 3.85 (m, 6H).

Other 2-arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones (1) were prepared by following method A or B. Their characterization data are recorded in Table I.

2-(2'-Methyl-5'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-5'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone-1,1-dioxide (2b) : A solution of 1.0 g potassium permanganate in 30 ml water was added dropwise with stirring to 2-(2'-methyl-5'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-5'-chloro)phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (0.6 g) dissolved in 20 ml glacial acetic acid. The addition was complete in 30 min. Aqueous sodium bisulphite was then added to the reaction mixture until it was colourless. The tan coloured precipitate was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 235°

TABLE 1—2-ARYLIMINO-3-ARYL-5-METHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (1)* AND 2-ARYLIMINO-3-ARYL-5-METHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINONE-1,1-DIOXIDES (2)*

Sl. no.	Substituents		Method	Yield %	m.p. °C
	X	Y			
1a	2-CH ₃	6-Cl	A/B	80	144
1b	2-CH ₃	5-Cl	A/B	70	124
1c	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	A	48	97
1d	4-OH ₂	3-Cl	A/B	45	77
1e	2-Cl	3-Cl	A	48	123
1f	2-Cl	4-Cl	A	55	128
1g	2-Cl	5-Cl	A/B	82	164
1h	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	A/B	60	191
1i	4-OCH ₃	3-Cl	A	78	76
2a	2-OH ₂	6-Cl	—	70	147
2b	2-OH ₂	5-Cl	—	70	235
2g	2-Cl	5-Cl	—	60	159
2h	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	—	70	183

* Spectral data (nmr and ir) in accord with their structures ; satisfactory analyses for N and S.

(Found : C, 52.5 ; H, 4.1 ; N, 7.2 ; S, 7.7. C₁₃H₁₀Cl₂N₂O₂S calcd. C, 52.6 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 6.8 ; S, 7.8%) ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1745m, 1720m, 1685s, 1645m, 1595m, 1310m, 1135m cm⁻¹.

Similarly other 2-arylimino-3-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone-1,1-dioxides (2) were prepared. Their yield, melting point and analytical data are listed in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of 2-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (1c) : Formation of 3-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindione (3c) : To a solution of 1.0 g 2-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone in 20 ml ethanol, 5 ml strong HCl was added and the mixture refluxed on a water bath for 36 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the product was poured into water and filtered. The residue was washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol to give 3-(2'-methyl-3'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindione (55%), m.p. 128° (Found : C, 46.1 ; H, 3.5 ; N, 6.2 ; S, 10.8. C₁₁H₁₀ClNO₂S calcd. C, 45.9 ; H, 3.5 ; N, 6.1 ; S, 11.1%) ; IR ν_{\max} (nujol) 1750m, 1680s, 1580m, 1500m cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 7.03-7.58 (m, 3H), 4.30 (q, J 7Hz, 1H), 1.75 (d, J 7Hz, 3H), 2.13 (s, 3H).

All the 3-aryl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindiones (3) reported in Table 2 were prepared from the hydrolytic cleavage of 1 in ethanolic HCl medium except 3e and 3g. The latter were obtained by hydrolysis of 1e and 1g, respectively, in acetic acid with strong HCl. The time required for the hydrolysis of 1 to give the corresponding 3, and the yield, melting point, and analytical data of 2,4-thiazolidindiones are recorded in Table 2.

Experiments under similar conditions failed to hydrolyse 2-(2'-methyl-6'-chloro)phenylimino-3-(2'-methyl-6'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (1a), and that 3-(2'-methyl-6'-chloro)phenyl-5-methyl-2,4-thiazolidindione could not be prepared. Hydrolysis of 1a with strong HCl did not occur even in a

TABLE 2—3-(DISUBSTITUTED)ARYL-5-METHYL-2,4-THIAZOLIDINDIONES (3)*

Sl. no.	Substituents		Reaction time h.	Yield %	M.p. °C
	X	Y			
3b	2-CH ₃	5-Cl	24	70	75
3c	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	36	55	128
3d	4-CH ₃	3-Cl	10	60	112
3e	2-Cl	3-Cl	36	70	137
3f	2-Cl	4-Cl	36	75	76
3g	2-Cl	5-Cl	36	50	113
3h	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	6	75	110
3i	4 OCH ₃	3-Cl	6	68	146

* Footnote as in Table 1.

higher boiling alcohol, glycerol, at a temperature 270° by heating for 8 h.

Fungicidal activity screening : All the nine 4-thiazolidinones (1) and seven out of eight 2,4-thiazolidindiones (3) except 3f were evaluated for their antifungal activity against two typical agricultural fungi *Trichoderma viride* and *Curvularia lunata* by agar growth food poison technique at dilutions of 1 : 1000 and 1 : 5000 (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF 2-ARYLIMINO-3-ARYL-5-METHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (1) AND 3-ARYL-5-METHYL-2,4-THIAZOLIDINDIONES (3)

Medium, Czapek's agar ; Time, 4 days ; Temp., 25±1°

Sl. no.	% Inhibition of <i>Trichoderma viride</i> at dilutions		% Inhibition of <i>Curvularia lunata</i> at dilutions	
	1 : 1000	1 : 5000	1 : 1000	1 : 5000 ¹
	1a	29	21	50
1b	39	15	24	17
1c	35	19	63	28
1d	39	22	47	32
1e	55	34	60	10
1f	43	34	54	44
1g	21	19	50	17
1h	51	43	50	24
1i	41	18	60	30
3b	100	78	100	73
3c	100	80	84	77
3d	100	71	100	73
3e	86	46	84	44
3g	88	58	80	47
3h	82	60	84	63
3i	100	60	84	57
Cuman*	27 (34)	16 (20)	57 (71)	50 (62)

* Values in parentheses denote the extrapolated percentage inhibition of the standard fungicide for 100% Ziram content.

Results and Discussion

It is concluded from the screening results that 2,4-thiazolidindiones (3) are more active fungicides against both the fungi in comparison to a standard commercial fungicide Cuman (80% Ziram). On the other hand, 4-thiazolidinones (1) inhibit fungus growth more or less to the same extent as Cuman.

For a given set of substituents, the 2,4-thiazolidindiones (3) containing only one aryl group are

more fungicidal than the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (1) containing two aryl groups. This indicates that the fungicidal effect is basically due to the presence of a thiazolidinone nucleus and that the substituents present in the aryl group only modify the activity to some extent. A vacant 2-position in 3 presumably makes the active site more freely available for attack on the fungus and thereby it checks fungal growth to a greater extent. Among the tested compounds 3b, 3c and 3d are found to be the most effective.

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